

Advantages of Evaluating Frontal Bone Fractures in MDCT using 3-Dimensional and Coronal Reformatted Images Instead of Axial Images

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Abstract:

Background: CT scan has modified imaging especially in maxillofacial region having a complex and intricate anatomy in human body. It is now the most acceptable choice of imaging modality for diagnosis of facial bone fractures produced due to trauma.

Aim of the study: The study aimed to outline the benefits of utilizing 3-Dimensional and coronal reformatted images compared to axial images when assessing frontal bone fractures. Materials and methods: This study was carried out in the tertiary care centre located in North India. Frontal bone, using a 128 –Slice CT scanner; GE Revolution machine 128. Coronal multiplanar reformatted (MPR) and 3D volume-rendered images were also reconstructed to assess and characterize its benefits over standard axial images. Results: For the majority of patients, 3D images were on par with or better than axial images. It was discovered that coronal images were either comparable to or better at detecting fractures.

Conclusion: This study showed the benefits of 3D and coronal images over axial images for the assessment of frontal bone fracture as well as the usefulness of multidetector CT in the evaluation of frontal bone fractures.

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Introduction

Fractures of facial region elucidate substantial visits of emergency department in the world & are allied to great magnitude of morbidity & mortality attributable to damage of facial tissues, associated complications, in addition to trauma related to other parts of body. [1]

The severity of diagnosis of facial injuries is gradually increasing with the advancing trauma care, fractures of maxillofacial area can be clinically suspected in a traumatic patient in accordance with certain clinical signs. Albeit overlying oedema, haemorrhage and changes of soft tissue may initially conceal such signs. [2]

The maxillofacial area is amongst the most complicated anatomical regions in human body, and it is also linked to a number of crucial daily processes.

3D volume-rendered images and coronal multi planar reformatted (MPR) images were reconstructed to assess and describe its advantages over routine axial images for detection of fractures. Coronal images were found to be similar or superior in the detection of fractures.

Determining the precise nature of facial fractures and related soft tissue injuries in clinical practice

requires knowledge of the normal radiographic architecture of the facial skeleton in conjunction with appropriate clinical radiography evaluation. The best delineation of fracture patterns is possible when axial and coronal computed tomographic images are combined. The clinical and surgical management of patients with facial injuries benefits from this information. [3]

Plain radiography is the initial imaging modality in trauma patients, but in maxillofacial trauma, its importance in determining the extent of damage has decreased.

In emergency radiology MDCT is the imaging modality of choice and most authentic investigation in evaluating individuals with maxillofacial trauma in addition to detection of intracranial complications.

In addition to requiring a higher exposure level than traditional conventional radiography, MDCT facilitates the precise identification of number of fractures with locations and extents as well as the displacement of fracture segments and its degree of rotation.

It also helps in diagnosis of soft tissue injuries and skull base inclusion in the least amount of time. [4]

The remarkable spatial resolution of MDCT enables 3-D reconstructions and Multiplanar Reformations (MPR), which also offers superior diagnostic accuracy and great information regarding the comminution and displacement of bony fragments. Evaluation of complicated fractures in multiple planes can aid in better surgical planning and management. [5]

Materials and Methods

This was a prospective observational study which was conducted from January 2023 to August 2024 in a tertiary care centre located in North India.

Sampling Technique: Every eligible case matching the inclusion and exclusion criteria was included in the study

Inclusion Criteria: All patients of 10-65-year age group of both gender with clinical evidence of facial injuries who undergo Multi Detector Computed Tomography examination and are detected to be positive for fracture. Exclusion Criteria: Uncooperative and extremely debilitated patients and patients with facial injuries in whom a CT examination is contraindicated.

Methodology: An observational study was conducted after approval from Institutional ethical

committee. Following the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria, patients were chosen. Prior to examination, written and verbal informed consent was taken from the patient. Enrolment, recording of baseline information and MDCT was done for each patient.

Patient preparation and Technique: Patients were first positioned supine, then a lateral tomogram was taken to determine facial region to be investigated. Subsequently, region ranging from chin to a point 4–5 cm above supraorbital margins was subjected to a continuous volume scan with 5mm thickness of the axial section. The tomographic data was then transferred to the computer console. In conjunction with axial images, coronal MPR images were generated with 0.5 mm increments, 3 D volume-rendering images were also procured. The GE workstation was used to review MDCT scans. The fractures discovered on CT were categorized based on their location of involvement. Fracture detection, extent, as well as displacement were all assessed using 3D imaging compared to axial scans. For the purpose of detecting fractures, axial and coronal pictures were compared.

Tabulation of data provided by 3D / coronal image comparable to axial image.

Score	3D/Coronal assessment
A	Subservient to axial image (IA)
B	Equivalent to axial image (SA)
C	Prevailing- equivalent information more rapidly assimilated (SS)
D	Prevailing-additional conceptual information provided (SU)

Illustration of Cases

Case 1- Frontal bone Fracture

Figure 1: A- Three dimensional rendered images, B- Axial and C- Coronal computed tomography image showing comminuted depressed fracture involving inner and outer tables of right frontal bone (arrows) with (arrowhead) impacted bony fragment

Case 2- Frontal bone Fracture

Figure 2: A- Three dimensional rendered image, B and C- Axial computed tomography images illustrating comminuted depressed frontal bone fracture involving outer and inner table of frontal sinus (blue arrows) with resultant hemosinus with displaced bony fragments in the frontal sinuses (arrowhead) and the fracture is extending to bilateral orbital roof with resultant bilateral pneumo-orbit (asterisk) and comminuted un-displaced fracture of medial wall of right orbit.

Observations & Results

Fractures Involving Frontal Bone

Comparison of 3-dimensional image to axial image for fracture detection

Score	Percentage
A	15
B	25
C	50
D	10

Comparison of 3-dimensional image to axial image for fracture extent

Score	Percentage
A	10
B	35
C	35
D	20

Comparison of 3-dimensional image to axial image for fracture displacement

Score	Percentage
A	10
B	35
C	35
D	20

4-Comparison of coronal images to axial images for fracture detection

Score	Percentage
A	5
B	80
C	10
D	5

In most cases, frontal bone fractures were detectable and displaced with fine perception on three-dimensional imaging. Nevertheless, 3-D images were incompetent in depicting fracture extension into posterior wall of sinus as well as roof of orbit. In detecting fractures of frontal bone, coronal & axial images were identical

Discussion

In 2001, TANRIKULU and EROL analysed clinical value of CT versus plain radiographs on 40 patients & concluded the excellence of CT in identification as well as categorization of all fractures. [6]

MDCT is principal imaging modality and precise investigation in examination of patients with craniofacial trauma. [7]

The exceptional spatial resolution of MDCT enables multiplanar reformations (MPR) and 3-D reconstructions, which improve surgical planning and diagnostic accuracy. [2] 3-D reconstruction and multiplanar reformation in the coronal and sagittal planes are useful for evaluating the bone architecture of fractures that are comminuted, displaced, or complicated fractures that span several planes. Since MPR and 3-D reconstructions may be obtained from the original 2D pictures without requiring patients to undergo further radiation exposure, MDCT is the recommended imaging technology for maxillofacial injuries.

MDCT is helpful for detection of exact site, number, extent of fractures, displaced fracture fragments with soft tissue injuries. [8, 9, 10] Accurate and prompt diagnosis permits efficient management of maxillofacial traumas consequently preventing the primary and secondary complications.

Present study comprised 72 patients who encountered frontal bone injury. The analysis covered patients evaluated with a 128-slice MDCT scanner. Frontal bone is notably prominent and

generally get injured in individuals presenting with maxillo-facial trauma. These fractures may be either due to direct trauma or due to an extension of a skull fracture.

Frontal bone fractures might affect both the anterior and posterior sinus walls or only the anterior or posterior table alone. Highly complicated fractures involving anterior along with posterior frontal sinus tables are customarily interrelated with other midfacial or skull fractures. [2]

Anterior table fractures are frivolous and generally do not require treatment whereas complex anterior & posterior table fractures are grave owing to association with skull fractures & central nervous system involvement. Pneumocephalus is usually associated with posterior table fractures and reporting of degree of bone loss in posterior sinus wall & pneumocephalus is important because it indicates the probability of anterior cranial fossa involvement. [11]

3-Dimensional imaging was excellent in assessing the identification and displacement of frontal bone fractures in 50% & 35% of patients of this study. The 3-D scans were insufficient for evaluating the extent of the fracture, only if it extended into the orbit's roof or the posterior wall of sinus. This is ascribable to overlay of bony anterior wall of sinus hampering complete visibility. In the identification of frontal bony fractures, coronal imaging is comparable to axial scans.

Conclusion

MDCT being a precise approach is the current modality of choice for evaluating victims with craniofacial injuries. MDCT provides benefit of increased availability and speedy acquisition in event of acute trauma. MPR & 3-Dimensional VR images aid precise assessment of fractures encountered on axial scans.

This analysis determines significance of MDCT in assessment of Frontal bone trauma. An attempt has been made to detect & localize exact number, region of frontal bone fractures on axial, 3-D & coronal images. The improved fracture detection in frontal bone in conjunction with their displacement and extent in subjects with frontal bone fractures was feasibly documented.

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